

Vhembe Biosphere Reserve NPC

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United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
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In association with:

Statement on mining and related activities, 11th August 2014

The Board of directors of the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve considers that the potential extent of development of in particular coal mining and its associated activities within its geographical area and the cumulative impact that will likely result **are not compatible** with the aims and objectives of the UNESCO Man and the Biosphere programme, based as it is on principles of **conservation** and **sustainable** development.

The Board of Directors of the Vhembe Biosphere note with concern:

1. The extensive plans for extraction of coal resources by Coal of Africa, particularly along the ecologically high value northern foothills of the Soutpansberg.
2. The reneging by Coal of Africa on commitments made to the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve to undertake a cumulative impact assessment of all mining projects in the area.
3. Extensive prospecting applications in the ecologically high value areas of the Blouberg massif and Makgabeng plateau, the latter also characterised by unique heritage resources.
4. Prospecting over an extensive area of the Limpopo Valley for potential hydraulic fracturing to gain access to coal bed methane.
5. The resultant negative effect of the extensive mining including;
 - a. a massive strain on the already inadequate water resources
 - b. the need for major upgrading of infrastructure development particularly in regard to the road and rail system in order to transport the coal
 - c. the construction of high voltage power lines throughout the area and the visual and environmental effect on the area including the threatened vulture colonies.
6. The substantial reduction in the area of the Mapungubwe World Heritage Site buffer zone.
7. The granting of a mining licence within Venetia Nature Reserve, a *de facto* conservation area.

8. The granting of prospecting licences within Provincial Nature Reserves that have not been gazetted.
9. The announcement of plans for a coal fired power station in the Musina area.
10. A large number of other prospecting and mining applications within the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve area.
11. The fact that the 2013 Limpopo Conservation Plan avoids mining and prospecting applications as a cost factor and is not a true representation of biodiversity and ecosystem services values.

The absence of consideration and consultation with the VBR is extremely worrying given that the Vhembe District and Blouberg Local Municipality fall within the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve that was nominated to UNESCO ***with provincial and national government approval.***

The Board of Directors of the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve request National, Provincial and Local Government authorities and sector departments to convene an urgent meeting to discuss the lack of an integrated regional development plan within the region.

The Board of Directors of the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve reserves the right to approach UNESCO directly for assistance and advice with regard to the challenges of unsustainable development.

The 2013 Vhembe Biosphere Reserve Position Statement on Mining is appended.

Appendix: Vhembe Biosphere Reserve Position Statement on Mining, 2013.

Introduction

The Vhembe Biosphere Reserve (VBR) aims to represent all stakeholders within its area of responsibility and accommodates a cross section of interest groups in the furtherance of its vision of long term sustainable development. Mining is already a reality within the borders of the VBR and has become and will continue to be a key challenge to the new biosphere reserve given the interest by mining companies in the resources of the Limpopo Valley, particularly coal but also diamonds and gas.

The VBR includes a number of sensitive natural environments including areas of high biodiversity and eco-system services. It is also an area of great cultural and spiritual significance. Of concern is that it is a water stressed region that is home to large, poor rural communities with relatively few economic opportunities. It includes several towns and the main economic activities are commercial agriculture, game farming, hunting and tourism. It also contains significant mineral deposits, mainly coal and diamonds and the present limited mining activities are expected to increase significantly in the near future.

Within this scenario it is imperative that an uncompromising sustainable development strategy be implemented and this is the objective of the VBR and the Position Paper and Position Statement on Mining. These documents do not imply support by the VBR of mining in general nor do they imply support of any specific mining application. The VBR will strongly oppose any mining activity that does not adequately address the environmental impact or the impact on the well-being of human populations. This position paper or any financial or other support by mining companies for the work of the VBR will not jeopardize the objectives of the VBR in any way.

VBR position on mining

Societies worldwide are increasingly calling for a more sustainable mining policy and also for mining to contribute in a meaningful way towards benefit sharing, particularly towards local communities. The VBR strongly supports this call.

The International Council for Mining and Metals (“ICMM”) provides clear guidelines in this regard and distinguishes between the legal licence to operate (ie compliance and impact mitigation) and the social licence to operate (ie contribution towards sustainable development). See Appendix I: The 10 ICCM Principles.

Context

Legal Compliance is a given – mining companies must comply with the laws of the land. Impact mitigation is frequently presented as sustainable development. The VBR agrees with the ICMM guidance on this issue and agrees that impact mitigation and sustainable development are two separate issues each with their own processes and requirements. The National Environmental Management Act is also clear in this regard: any company that might impact negatively on the environment must anticipate and prevent such impacts, otherwise minimise and ultimately remedy any residual impacts. If there was no mine, there would be no impacts to mitigate. Included within the ambit of impact mitigation, the VBR supports innovative initiatives in regard to reduction of water footprint, reduction of energy use and land rehabilitation activities.

Sustainable development

The VBR holds the position that mining is an extractive industry and is therefore by definition not sustainable in and of itself. Furthermore, the use of coal in particular contributes to pollution, raised CO² levels and is increasingly seen as being highly contrary to sustainable development paths. However, the VBR recognises that mining can be a contributor to creating sustainable development opportunities within its zone of influence while taking into account the conservation of the environment and ensuring real, tangible benefits to affected communities.

The ICMM guidance is clear as regards what it terms a “contribution perspective”. If a mine extracts one form of Capital (a non-renewable mineral resource) then it must invest in increasing other forms of Capital over time so as to leave a net positive impact in its’ host community.

The VBR acknowledges that besides the ICMM guidance, there are many other national and international protocols and best practice guidelines that complement the ICMM guidelines in respect of sustainable development. These should be applied based on the individual needs and circumstances.

The VBR’s function is to represent the stakeholders in its area and to facilitate an interaction between mining and related companies in order to ensure balanced and long-term sustainable development of the area.

Conclusion and recommendation

The VBR accepts that it is a requirement that all mines within its’ broad area of influence, operate in compliance with the law and abide by the ICMM guidelines as regards impact mitigation and sustainable development.

When considering any mining in the VBR cognizance **must** be taken of:

- The broader macro implications of any individual mining application.
- Respect for the environment and heritage and the concept of ‘no-go’ areas for mining, particularly sensitive Heritage Landscapes, Core Areas and in Buffer Zones and ecological corridors.
- The precarious situation of water resources in the region and the fact that mining is a competitor with communities and agriculture for scarce supplies.
- The need for off-set benefits to be allocated to broad-based stakeholder communities and groups to contribute towards socio-economic upliftment.
- The need for mining to take account of the process whereby broad-based stakeholder communities are (and will continue to) realising their assets in terms of restituted land and developing sustainable livelihoods on this land.
- Public perceptions that present laws are insufficient and that there are serious flaws regarding allocation of resources to mining companies and the operation and closure of mines.
- Lastly, the VBR has proposed the establishment of a ‘Vhembe Mining Forum’ comprising all of the mining companies operating in the region and with whom the VBR can facilitate realistic, widespread stakeholder engagement on the issues raised.

Appendix I: The 10 ICMM Principles

- 1) Implement and maintain ethical business practices and sound systems of corporate governance.
- 2) Integrate sustainable development considerations within the corporate decision-making process.
- 3) Uphold fundamental human rights and respect cultures, customs and values in dealings with employees and others who are affected by our activities.
- 4) Implement risk management strategies based on valid data and sound science.
- 5) Seek continual improvement of our health and safety performance.
- 6) Seek continual improvement of our environmental performance.
- 7) Contribute to conservation of biodiversity and integrated approaches to land use planning.
- 8) Facilitate and encourage responsible product design, use, re-use, recycling and disposal of our products.
- 9) Contribute to the social, economic and institutional development of the communities in which we operate.
- 10) Implement effective and transparent engagement, communication and independently verified reporting arrangements with our stakeholders.

For a more detailed explanation of these 10 principles please see the ICMM website at: <http://www.icmm.com/our-work/sustainable-development-framework/10-principles> or the document “**Draft for Discussion: VBR Position Paper on Mining in the VBR**” dated August 2012.